

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING GEOMETRIC MATERIALS

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Abstract: This article is aimed at increasing the mathematical literacy of elementary school students, introducing them to geometrically simple materials, and explaining the methodological aspects used in this regard. In this place, at these stages, the practical work required of teachers has been scientifically researched.

Keywords: geometry, shapes, point, section, angle, simple shapes, many angles.

Geometry is Greek from the word received is land _ and I measure said the meaning means _ Mathematics subject forms and shaped relationships who learns department . That place to measure with depends respectively appear was _ For example , open cylindrical the dish shape , size , surface face of geometry learning are its objects color or how from substance made while to geometry about concepts not .

Primary class to his students geometry the word and his meaning about concepts not given perhaps geometric forms another words through represents _ For example : polygons , shapes , flat forms , spatial forms ;

Primary class students are the first of the 1st grade with a point from the steps meet they start Initially What is the point to the students ? the fact that is explained and hand rhetoric development in order to checkered fill in notebooks _ _ is asked . In this students point wider and visible by doing paint their writing can _ If the dots filling to the error road if they put it , a teacher by of the notebook red of the line beyond to the part mistakes corrected situation example by doing to show possible will be

Numbers to write preparation according to stand up , students teacher as shown

below practical the assignment do : the point of the cell in between put (cell in the lower left corner , box from the sides one's in the middle and others); placed points example according to combine .
For example : Point of the cell in the middle of the cell right to the corner , box bottom side of in the middle put and this points succession _ _ with combine .

That's right line with from acquaintances then , students point right to the line to put , given one , two or three from the points right line transfer , point right to the line relatively situation exactly to determine that's it practical affairs help gives _

First point, section , fracture in class line such as topics with they get to know each other . They are mathematics study in the process lines right and broken to the lines division knowing they get That 's right on the line lying down from the point past line right line , one right on the line didn't sleep from the points past line broken line that they distinguish Also to students as follows assignments are also given : to your notebook desired three put an optional period and they are through first as desired right line transfer _ In this situation two different condition to be can _

's right on the line lying 3 points, one right on the line 3 points that do not lie .

That's right line cross section with from being introduced then similar _ assignments dot and cross section with will be done . For example , the length is 6 cm, 3 cm cuts draw _

Polygons make them _ elements with while dating students of the polygon ends points to draw knowing they get

For example : Tasks do :

1. Side 2 cm was square draw _
2. The sides are 2 cm and 3 cm was rectangle draw _

Class I in students right line about imaginations different practical exercises perform in the process is formed . In this right line curve line with is compared . For example , string a thread (hemp) . by doing is drawn , then thread hanging

standing by doing will be released ; let's say right way 1 and curve (path) no1 is described picture viewed , folded paper sheet bending line according to it is hard . Anyway _ line right line or curve line harvest that it was is determined . Children from the ruler using is correct the line to spend to get it is necessary Similar to this practical The subject of work in the 1st grade with from acquaintance after they do . First cuts they measure and they draw Practical exercises perform in the process children right of the line some properties with they get to know each other . For example , through the point line transfer exercise while doing children own their observations summarize through one point _ as desired right and curve lines transfer possible ; through two points one right and as desired curve lines transfer can _

That's right line section students with _ in practice get acquainted : students of the teacher from behind right lines and right line cuts in drawings they show and themselves they draw , cut limited that is true line while that it is not limited , on paper his one piece drawing little by little they understand . Don't cut of the concept to be strengthened such practical exercises help gives : two point cross section with connection ; one right on the line lying down through three points cross section transfer , in this harvest was all cuts show _ Cuts to measure until equal to and equal to did not happen cuts about concepts is entered , this relationships determination method-over to put is explained . Later , centimeter , decimeter , meter and others with from acquaintance after students cuts to measure and to draw circle a lot practical exercises they do .

Polygons to make in the process of his from the elements one cross section that trust fruit they do

Pupils in the 2nd grade times with designation with from acquaintances after written-practical exercises given , such exercises another of cuts piece was cuts separate get as well as another from cuts Created cuts separate get read strengthens _

Little by little students cross section one how many of the polygon side to be

possible they understand and to this based on II-IV grades polygons inside new figures harvest will be by doing cuts to make circle exercises they do ; for example , in your notebook so two rectangle draw and them one cross section so transfer so that : a) of course right rectangle and one triangle harvest let b) be one square and another rectangle harvest let it be Such exercises in children thinking ability and spatial imaginations develops , as well as geometric concepts strengthens _

1st grade students broken line with cross section to the concept relying on will be introduced . Teacher of children the eye in front long the grass or wire into pieces breaking broken of the line model preparation can _ On the board broken the line sometimes one right on the line didn't sleep nails to the points drawn colorful yarn using is shown . Students on the board and in his notebooks broken the line they draw That 's right on the line they put 3, 4, 5 points that are not lying down and them cuts with they connect . Students are always broken line how many from the incision consists of or in it how many section that there is they count Practical the work in the process closed and not closed broken lines differentiating they get Exercises in the process closed broken line with this broken line limit was polygon between connection is determined . Three from the department consists of broken line triangle , four from the department consists of broken line rectangle limits .

Primary in classes geometry elements in learning the studied material system features account received without , his separately directions separate to get important importance occupation because _ _ study must was of exercises content and character to determine chance by creating concrete in class of them which one main and which one introduction character have that to determine help gives _ For example , start school mathematics in the chair basically cross section concept study in the eye filled . This is a concept about imagination harvest to do for « right from the concept of "line " . use need will be But such teacher right line concept with students to introduce necessary said conclusion come not coming out

because it is necessary this without basically the goal students cross section with introduction is correct _ line concept only dating character have will be That's why for students _ short is correct line and curve lines with from being introduced after their cross section about knowledge deep and justified respectively content will be found .

In students right line about initial the imagination content find for to the board three student taken out , two student chalk smeared thread to the board two to the point put tight holding stands , third student while thread tense pulling standing up put sends , as a result on the board right line one part of image harvest will be Both of them towards continue carry on possible class to his students is explained .

Students right line with introduction with one in line curve line with (compare based on) to be introduced good the result gives _ For example , if tense drawn yarn to the board right line track left if it is a curve line about imagination harvest to do for it is cool to the situation is brought and left trace curve line about imagination gives _

In students right line and curve line about simple imaginations content after being found , now they are right the line ruler using to make with will be introduced .

Students right line about imaginations conscious and right content in finding only horizontal drawn right from the lines without using it , maybe vertical or slope without right lines drawing is also important important has _ A lot cases vertical drawn right lines students understand they don't get it drawn right lines and « slope line » or some in cases « curve they also call it " line " . Students right line and curve of lines some one properties with introduction is also a goal is appropriate . For example , students one how many exercises perform as a result through a point as desired right and curve line transfer possible , through two points as desired curve line transfer maybe , but through two points only one right line transfer possible said to the conclusion they come That's right line about in students imagination harvest in doing paper sheet

from folding use important important has _ In this of students attention paper sheet where method do not fold the result everything is one one different to be , that is right line image harvest to be focus it is necessary

That's right line and curve line about in students imaginations harvest done , now them right line section about imaginations harvest to do transition can _ It is also practical from work use recommendation done : on the board tense drawn thread scissors with trimmed , right line section about initial imagination harvest will be done . Students to their notebooks drawn right to the line border by putting two dots that's it from the points consists of was right of the line section or short without cross section harvest to be realize they are enough . Geometric figures in defining from the letters use from included after now cross section in defining two from the letter use that it is possible and this letters don't cut to the end put about concept is given and "DE cut " is written and points D and E don't cut the ends means about information is given Primary classes mathematics course to the program basically of cuts lengths to measure and to compare big attention is given If initially of cuts lengths cells according to and scalable ruler using done if increased , later cross section the length and scalable ruler using to measure done is increased .

In students cuts lengths to measure and comparison skills content given after receiving to length cuts to make , right rectangle to make circle issues solve the way with their knowledge skill and qualifications is strengthened . Don't cut about imaginations strengthening for students them wrapping woven from the environment right line cross section to show circle exercises with (board edges , with a ceiling walls connected places , go away edge and etc.) introduction is also important importance occupation is enough

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